

FULL FIELD INSPECTION OF COMPOSITE COMPONENTS USING NATURAL FREQUENCY EXCITATION

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ABSTRACT

Thermoelastic stress analysis (TSA) is an established active thermographic approach which uses the thermoelastic effect to relate the temperature change that occurs as a material is subjected to elastic cyclic loading to the sum of the principal stresses on the surface of the component. Digital image correlation (DIC) tracks features on the surface of a material to establish a displacement field from a component subjected to load, which can then be used to calculate the strain field. Laboratory based loading for TSA and DIC is typically imparted using a test machine, in the current work a vibration-based loading system is used which excites the component of interest at resonant frequency which enables TSA and DIC to be carried out. In the present paper a composite plate is subject to resonant frequency loading using a portable loading device, i.e. 'remote loading'. Complimentary information is extracted from the two techniques. The work provides a step towards a combined strain based non-destructive evaluation procedure able to identify and quantify the effect of defects more fully, particularly when examining component performance in service applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use full field inspection techniques enable a more complete inspection of a region of interest when compared to more traditional point measurement techniques such as strain gauges. Recent improvements in the performance of optical systems and increased computational power have led to an increased interest in the use of optical techniques for full field assessment. Digital image correlation (DIC) ^[1] has become a very popular technique used to assess displacement or strain fields on a structure that has experienced a change in applied load. Typically a speckle pattern is applied to the surface of a component. The speckle pattern is recorded for an unloaded and loaded case using a white light camera. A correlation algorithm is then applied to track the speckle pattern throughout loading and hence determine a displacement field which may then be converted into a strain map enabling regions of concern to be identified. DIC is limited in spatial resolution and so areas with high displacement or strain gradients, such as around defects, are not well resolved, without resorting to high magnification optics and hence limiting the field of view. Thermoelastic stress analysis (TSA) ^[2] is an established active thermographic technique which uses an infrared detector to monitor the thermal response of components as they are subjected to a cyclic load. The applied load signal from the load cell is then used in a lock-in algorithm with the thermal data from an infra-red detector to provide the temperature change, which can then be converted to the sum of the principal stresses. TSA has high spatial resolution but can only provide the principal stress sum, which is not a failure criterion. By using the two techniques a more complete picture of the structural response to loading is obtained.

In DIC loading generally occurs at a relatively slow rate relative to the frame rate of the camera i.e. as load rates increase the preference is to use camera systems with lower spatial resolution and increase frame rate of data collection ^[3]. When considering the monitoring of cyclically loaded components, such as during fatigue tests, it is preferable to not pause the test to enable data collection as this would extend the duration of the tests and may introduce anomalies, particularly if extended dwell times are used whilst under load. The majority of work covering the application of DIC to cyclic

loading involves the synchronisation of data capture to the peak loads of the sinusoidal load signal ^[4] although this found to add complexity and cost to tests. As typical tests may be carried out using a single frequency load the current work uses the lock-in approach, well established in TSA, to construct the DIC data relative to the loading frequency ^[5]. The lock-in processing enables cameras with lower frame rates to be used and thus a cost efficient approach may be found. The established lock-in technique used in TSA is based on the use of a fast Fourier transform to relate the applied cyclic load to the thermoelastic cyclic response. In ^[5] strain data is extracted using a single camera setup examining in plane strains in a Brazilian disc, the present paper uses the lock-in approach with stereo DIC to study the mechanical behaviour of composite components.

When considering the inspection of structures in service it is no longer possible to rely on load imparted through the use of a laboratory based test machine. The practicalities of in-situ loading and robust inspection must be considered. Natural frequency excitation has previously been successfully used to inspect cantilever beams and clamped plates using TSA ^[6]. The current work uses a vibration based remote loading system ^[7] to excite components at resonant frequencies to enable inspection.

Previous work has been successfully undertaken using TSA to inspect generic representative aircraft panels ^[8], shown in figure 1b, where the load was imparted using a servo hydraulic test machine and a specially designed rig that applied a cyclic pressure load to the panels. Further work showed that it was possible to use natural frequency excitation to capture TSA data from the same panel ^[9]. The thermoelastic response when loaded using natural frequency excitation was a factor of ten smaller than that of forced loading however when line plots are taken across the data, shown in figure 2, it was clear that the same stress concentrations are identified in both data sets. At that time it was not possible to achieve the same success with DIC. The work described in the present paper takes a step back from the previous work and focusses on the establishing the imaging techniques and remote loading approach on simpler plate specimens.

Figure 1: a) representative aircraft secondary structure panels ^[8] b) TSA ΔT data using forced loading and c) TSA ΔT using natural frequency excitation as presented in ^[9].

Figure 2: Line plots taken across aircraft panel data using forced and natural frequency loading ^[9].

The current paper investigates the behaviour of glass fibre reinforced plastic (GFRP) plates fixed along all edges. When considering the harmonic loading of the plate components typical first mode excitation frequencies are of the order of 100 Hz. Standard, lower cost, white light cameras have frame rates of a few Hertz. The aim of the current work is to use lower cost cameras, which under sample relative to the cyclic loading frequency, to collect images for use in DIC that can be correlated using a lock-in algorithm to provide displacement data from specimens subject to resonant frequencies, introduced as lock-in DIC (LIDIC). TSA and LIDIC are carried out for each plate experiencing the same loading conditions to enable a comparison of the two techniques. The mode shapes obtained by the two techniques are different: TSA provides the stress field induced by the modal excitation and the LIDIC identifies the displacement field.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Specimens and preparation

GFRP plates were manufactured using a 300gsm E-glass unidirectional epoxy prepreg. The plates were manufactured using three plies of the material [0, 90, 0], to give a plate thickness of 0.9 mm, with 0 along the short axis of the plate. Three of the plates contained simulated defects including a fold, a ply cut transverse to the fibres and a section of the ply removed – referred to as ‘box cut’. All simulated defects were created in the central ply. The rig comprised a frame that clamps the plate to a stand to model a fully built in plate. The dimensions of the unclamped area were 330 x 203 mm.

In TSA it is preferential to have a high and uniform emissivity surface. This is typically obtained by coating the surface of components with a thin layer of matt black paint. In DIC it is necessary to have a random pattern on the surface of a component which has sufficient contrast to enable tracking of the plate deformation. This is typically in the form of a spray paint speckle pattern. It is generally accepted^[10] that a white background with black speckles provides a higher level of contrast and the white background has a naturally higher grey level variation thus adding to the uniqueness of a subset compared to a black background. However when a white background speckle pattern was used an increased amount of reflections were visible in the thermal data. Therefore a black background with white speckles was selected, which did not have a noticeable effect on the TSA. To enable both DIC and TSA to be carried out without having to move or adjust the plate, potentially affecting the loading conditions, the speckle pattern was applied before any testing was carried out.

2.2 Data collection

A schematic of the experimental set up is provided in figure 3. A bolted steel frame was used to clamp the plates around the edges while inspection was carried out on the upper surface. The load was imparted into the plates using a permanent magnet shaker (LDS V201) which was positioned below the plate. The shaker was attached using a rigid stinger. The stinger was positioned at the location of the expected peak of displacement for the second mode as it was possible to excite both first and second modes from this position. A strong connection was made between the plate and the stinger using beeswax; this enabled easy removal and repositioning. A signal generator was used to excite the shaker while the lock in signal was collected using a force transducer attached to the stinger. The data and lock in signal were recorded using the appropriate white light or IR detector software. TSA was undertaken using a Cedip 420M IR detector capable of a maximum full frame rate of 383 Hz and has a listed thermal sensitivity of 20 mK. Using the lock-in technique this may be reduced to the order of 4 mK. The software used to collect and process the TSA data were Altair and Altair LI respectively. 3D DIC was carried out using two LaVision E-lite 5 MP cameras with 50 mm Nikon lenses. The data were collected and processed using the DaVis software. The DIC data were then exported to Matlab where the lock-in processing was performed.

The DIC data were processed using a subset size of 31 x 31 pixels with an overlap of 50%. The speckle size is visually estimated at 5-10 pixels per speckle with approximately 4-5 speckles per subset and 0.25 subsets per millimetre. Through processing 10 images collected without load the noise in the DIC data was found to be 0.004 mm for the z-displacement. However, it is noted that, as in TSA, the

use of the lock-in processing acts as a band pass filter thus enabling specific frequency signals to be extracted, greatly reducing the noise threshold.

Figure 3: Schematic of experimental set-up.

The basic rules of sampling ^[11] state that a whole number of cycles must be included in the data collection duration to avoid spectral leakage. Shannon's criterion ^[12] states that the sampling frequency must be twice that of the maximum excitation frequency to avoid aliasing. When considering the use of under sampling these rules must be adapted accordingly and sampling and excitation frequencies must be carefully selected to ensure a representative signal is reconstructed to avoid aliasing. Firstly it should be ensured that an integer number of periods of the reconstructed signal are collected. Secondly the loading frequency should not be an exact multiple of half of the sampling frequency which would result in a bias in the sampling position in the excitation signal resulting in aliasing. An additional consideration relating to the collection of data from a dynamic state is to select a short exposure or integration time relative to a period of loading to avoid blurring.

The excitation frequencies and sampling frequencies (frame rates) for first and second mode excitation are given in Table 1. The frame rate of the IR detector was fixed at the maximum full frame rate of 383 Hz for all experiments. The frame rate used in the LIDIC should varied according to the excitation frequency ensuring that the sampling criteria previously discussed were met. The integration time was fixed at 700 μ s for the IR detector and white light cameras to avoid blurring.

Mode	Excitation frequency (Hz)	TSA frame rate (Hz)	TSA data collection duration (s)	DIC frame rate (Hz)	DIC data collection duration (s)
1	90	383	5.2	1.5	200
2	110	383	5.2	1.5	200

Table 1: Excitation and sampling frequencies for mode one and two excitation.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Undamaged plate

The results for the GFRP control plate excited at its second mode are presented in figure 4. In figure 4a TSA data is presented as $\Delta T/T$ data which is directly related to the sum of the principal stresses and in figure 4d LIDIC data is presented in terms of out of plane displacement. Line plots taken horizontally across the centre of the plate in both data sets are shown in figures 4b and e. Finally the phase data relative to the reference data collected from the force transducer for both data sets is also shown which illustrates the synchronisation of the load signal and the recorded displacement / IR signal.

The effect of the stinger is apparent in the thermoelastic data where large concentrations in the response are visible in the $\Delta T/T$ data and the line plot, indicated in figure 4a. This concentration around the stinger location causes a bias in the TSA data compared to the expected form of two peaks of similar magnitude and shape. Aside from this concentration the TSA data appears to show the expected pattern for the excitation of the second mode in the control plate. The LIDIC displacement data also captures the mode shape. A decrease in spatial resolution is to be expected when comparing LIDIC and TSA as TSA uses each pixel recorded as a data point where as LIDIC requires pixel subsets thus reducing the number of data points. The LIDIC line plot taken across the plate provides a mode shape closer to that expected however it highlights that the stinger location is limiting the displacement of the left peak thus leading to a lower displacement measurement. This corresponds with the high stress concentration found in the TSA data. As expected the two halves of the plate are found to be out of phase with each other due to the second harmonic excitation. The TSA phase data in figure 4c is highlighting one half of the top surface is in compression while the other half is in tension while the LIDIC phase data in figure 4f is illustrating where half the plate has a positive displacement while the other is negative. The control plate modal excitation data sets give confidence in the success of the under sampling and lock-in approach used in the DIC data collection.

Figure 4 GFRP control plate second mode – TSA data a) $\Delta T/T$, b) $\Delta T/T$ horizontal profile at pixel 130 and c) phase data; LIDIC data d) z-displacement, e) z-displacement horizontal profile at subset 70 and f) phase data.

3.2 Box cut plate

The TSA and LIDIC data for the GFRP panel with the box cut in the central ply is provided in figure 5. The plate is excited at the same frequency as the control panel at 110 Hz, i.e. the expected natural frequency of an undamaged plate to allow comparison of the response of a damaged and undamaged component. The mode shape in both data sets is very different to that obtained for the control panel. The TSA $\Delta T/T$ data, given in figure 7a identifies the edges of the box cut as there is a local change in stiffness at the box cut. The box cut is also evident in the profile data taken across the centre of the plate shown in figure 5b. The LIDIC successfully identifies a change from the expected mode shape found in the control specimen

thus enabling the damage to be detected but not located. The box cut is visible in the TSA phase data but not in the LIDIC phase data. The change from the expected mode shape in the LIDIC data highlights the need to examine the data fully. It was found that the box feature is evident in some of the DIC displacement data prior to LIDIC processing as shown in figure 6 where the mode shape is not reconstructed.

Figure 5 GFRP plate with box cut section – TSA data a) $\Delta T/T$, b) $\Delta T/T$ horizontal profile at pixel 130 and c) phase data; LIDIC data d) z-displacement, e) z-displacement horizontal profile at subset 70 and f) phase data.

Figure 5: 3D DIC frame taken directly from DaVis showing the lower level data available which may be masked through use of the lock-in approach.

3 CONCLUSIONS

A remote loading technique based on excitation of harmonic modes of plates has been successfully trialled for both TSA and LIDIC. Loading frequencies far greater than sampling frequencies have been used resulting in a greatly under sampled data set. It has been shown that through selection of the correct sampling parameters it is possible to apply a lock-in algorithm to reconstruct the data and produce lock-in DIC taken during a dynamic cyclically loaded test. This is the first step towards using such low cost cameras for LIDIC. Further work is examining how to remove the expected modal displacements to enable discrepancies caused by defects to be highlighted in the LIDIC data. A further set of experiments exciting each plate at its own natural frequency will be carried out to establish the change in natural frequency.

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